

LIVELIHOOD ISSUES AND CHALLENGES FACED BY THE INHABITANTS OF PILIBHIT TIGER RESERVE

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Abstract- Pilibhit is a city and municipal board in the Pilibhit district in the Indian state of Uttar Pradesh, the most forest-rich area in North India. As of the 2011 India census, Pilibhit District had a population of 2,037,225 which makes it 226th most populous district out of 640 in India. Pilibhit Tiger Reserve was declared as the 46th Tiger reserve of India in June 2014 on the basis of its special type of ecosystem with vast open spaces and sufficient feed for the elegant predators. There are 219,592 families in Pilibhit district who depend on agriculture. From the time, the Tiger Reserve land was sanctioned; there has been sharp fall in the area available for agriculture, since almost half of the area suitable for agriculture has now been reserved for the Tiger Reserve. The current situation is that the economic conditions are very poor and most of the population lives below the poverty line.

This paper focuses on assessing the degree of dependence of these communities on the forest resources. Since, there is always fear of getting attacked by Big Cats, which majorly impacts the sources of income related to the forest. This paper is also about examining types of forest resources and mechanism of consumption, production & distribution of forest resources.

Keywords: Inhabitants, Tiger Reserve, Sources of Income, Unemployment, Animal Attacks, Poverty, Social Well Being

INTRODUCTION

Pilibhit is a city and municipal board in the Pilibhit district in the Indian state of Uttar Pradesh, the most forest-rich area in North India. "According to a report issued by the Government of India, Pilibhit is one of the *Minority Concentrated Areas in India* on the basis of the 2001 census data on population, socioeconomic indicators and basic amenities indicators. As of 2011 census, Males constitute 52.78% of the population and females 47.22%. Pilibhit has an average literacy rate of 63.58%, lower than the national average of 74.04%. Male literacy is 70.70%, and female literacy is 50.0%. In Pilibhit, 15.01% of the population is under 6 years of age." Rapidly increasing population and unemployment are the reasons of concern. Pilibhit has been granted to have a tiger reserve area, 63.7 kilometers away from the city boundary. This new tiger reserve at Pilibhit covers an area of approximately 1089 km² in Lagga-Bhagga Forest Range. Forests in Pilibhit have at least 48 tigers and a good predator base for their survival. Pilibhit forests are part of Terai forests, which together with grasslands constitute habitat for over 127 animals, 556 bird species and 2100 flowering plants.

The number of tigers in the Pilibhit Tiger Reserve is getting increased due to good atmospheric conditions and dense forest land. Since, the time the Tiger Reserve Area has been sanctioned by the government of India, the people of affected area are afraid of their economic and living conditions. There are 219,592 families in Pilibhit district, depending on agriculture. There has been steep fall in the area available for agriculture. Although the people still have enough area available for farming but they are afraid of going into their fields because of the fear of the wild animals. The economic conditions of the people living around the Tiger Reserve have been badly impacted because people are afraid of man-eating tigers which have taken lives of their loved ones. The current situation is that the economic conditions there are very poor and most of the population lives below the poverty line.

Fig 1: Pilibhit Tiger Reserve Area

Forest is a natural resource which is not only a source of biomass-based materials like food, fodder, timber, medicines, etc. but also has cultural, spiritual and religious values associated with it. Nevertheless, forests are integral to global weather systems and the world's oxygen supply and they serve as watersheds that absorb water and prevent soil erosion. Human dependency on forest has been defined as "people directly dependent on forest resources for livelihood". This category refers to people partially or wholly dependent on forest for subsistence. It does not include people dependent on the tree products from small private or village plots."

"Forest dependent" means dependent on wood, land & tree derived goods and services of a forest. The 'forest communities' referred here would mean the people living in the forest villages of Reserved Forests which came up as a necessity at the time that these forests were notified as Reserved Forests. A significant percentage of global population has a direct relationship with forest and trees. In every region of the world there are communities that live within or immediately adjacent to forested areas and who depend on them for sustenance. It has been estimated that one quarter of the world's poor depend directly or indirectly on forest for their livelihood. The nature of dependence varies in nature and pattern in different parts of the world. It is because of reasons more than these that such populations are dependent on forest resources.

Influence of better road network and closer links with the urban centers have created more livelihood opportunities in the recent past. However, the importance of forests for the people who are living in and around it is extensive. The understanding of these people of the forest is often overlooked. These communities, especially in developing countries are understandably dependent on forest resources at varying degrees while taking advantage of the apparent prosperity of the urban linkage. Forests are not only regarded as a source of timber, firewood, fodder and non-timber forest products but also for sustenance by the forest denizen.

Forests and the products are linked to household and livelihood systems in uncountable ways. Forest products commonly contribute to meeting food and other basic needs, are a source of supplementing inputs into the agricultural activities, help households control exposure to risk of various kinds and constitute an integral part of the habitat in conjunction to social and cultural structure of those living within that environment. It is, therefore, necessary to consider how usage or sale of material products such as forest foods is conditioned by this context of inter-relationships between people and the forest environment.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the living conditions of the villagers.
2. To study the impact of animal attacks on their social well being
3. To study the livelihood issues and challenges faced by them w.r.t forest resources

ANIMAL ATTACKS - A Major Factor Affecting the Social Well Being of Inhabitants

Pilibhit Tiger Reserve is home to many wild animals. The people of the nearby villages always live with the fear of tiger attack. In earlier times, these villagers were not much afraid despite the presence of the tigers, but according to them, "Since this reserve area has been sanctioned, man-eating tigers are also there". Also sudden increment in the tiger attack rates has also left them in dilemma. Now they are not allowed to go to the forestry land to get honey, fruits or even fire woods. The area has been banned for them to go in permanently.

Fig 2: A search party inside the forest in the Bankati range of the Pilibhit Reserve

In last few years, Tiger's intrusion in the areas of human presence has increased because of changes in the land use pattern. This has led to an unprecedented increase in human wildlife conflict.

Pilibhit is among the narrowest tiger reserves in India, and in many areas, crop fields along the edge merge almost seamlessly with the forests. These fields, especially when seen from the eyes of a wild cat species, are essentially grasslands, and they thereby extend wildlife habitats, and often serve as corridors. These hold water as these places are well irrigated, and shelter wild prey species such as pigs and hog deer; so are attractive for wild carnivores. It also clearly depicts that tiger population of Pilibhit is likely to be preying on humans more than any other tiger population in the region.

Fig 3: Data showing the number of deaths inside vs. outside of Tiger Reserve

Sustained observations of tigers in the farmlands of the villages outside Pilibhit area explicate that tigers can sometimes occur in close proximity to humans for extended periods, without attacking them. Recent attacks on humans in and around Pilibhit Tiger Reserve could thus primarily be attributed to one or two individuals that could be young individuals in marginal habitats without territories, older individuals with disabilities, or those with debilitating injuries. For instance, it has been reported in a section of the media that unlike other tiger habitats, humans live “check by jowl” with big cats in Pilibhit, and thus routinely fall victim to them. Until its creation in May 2014, the area was one of north India’s most productive timber-yielding reserve forests. The presence of tigers in these farmlands is thus neither surprising nor unexpected. For the most part, they move through such areas, silent and unseen under cover of darkness.

Fig 4: A Tiger hides behind long grass in the Pilibhit Tiger Reserve

The lack of toilets increases the vulnerability of villagers. Villagers say most tiger and leopard take place at the crack of dawn, when they go out for their ablutions. This is also the time when big cats are most active.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF INHABITANTS

The major issues of the inhabitants living nearby Pilibhit Tiger Reserve lies in their socio- economic conditions. There are many reasons why there conditions have been deteriorating.

Earlier, locals freely ventured into the forest to procure minor produce, fodder and to pluck a local delicacy 'katarua' (Indian wild truffle), edible fungi that grows near the root of Sal trees. Due to its limited availability, 'katarua' fetches handsome returns in the local market but now they are not allowed to enter in the forest range.

According to a report, *"The economic conditions of the villagers have worsen so much that they are sending elders of the family for animal prey so that they can get compensation by showing the dead-bodies to the forest officials."*

Fig 5: Pilibhit Tiger Reserve Area showing the Human-Animal Conflict

According to an environmentalist, “Everyone was dependent on the forest. Contractors for their money, administration for the revenue and locals for their day to day needs. Very few people cropped paddy in their fields, they used to buy rice and wheat from the money earned from selling wild fruits or their salary from the forest contractor they used to work for.”

Although the people still have enough area available for farming but they are either not allowed to go into their fields or they are too much afraid of the deadly attacks. The major issues of the inhabitants living nearby the Tiger Reserve are to maintain socio-economic conditions as well as saving their families from attacks of these big-cats. 17 people were killed by man-eating Tigers in Pilibhit in 2017 alone. The situation is so bad that sometimes the farmers are dragged from their houses by the tiger.

SUGGESTIONS & COCNLCUSION

In order to strengthen the living and economic condition of the villagers, the conservation and development programs need to pay better attention to the forest income on which so many rural people depend. Particular attention needs to be given where communities have little or no access to markets as their livelihood and poverty exiting options are much more limited. Also there should be fixed sources of income for the villagers, which would help them in living their life. Therefore interventions in these areas should focus primarily on livelihood-enhancing and community resilience-strengthening strategies.

The bottom line is that if policies of forest governance and officials ignore or undervalue the importance of non-cash forest income, it risks jeopardizing the day-to-day survival mechanisms of the poor, the livelihoods of the wealthier, and the achievement of poverty reduction goal. PTR’s administration should take steps to build rapid response teams comprising wildlife veterinarians, forest department staff, and local volunteers trained to contain conflict-prone animals and engage irate crowds. The local police too needs to be integrated into these response teams and assist in crowd control. Educators and public health professionals need to engage communities to enhance their preparedness for conflict and reduce casualties. Also building toilets can not only save human lives in forest areas, but aid conservation by addressing the problem of reprisal attacks by humans. There should be sustainable community awareness programs to reduce the risk of tiger attacks in farmlands.

Thus, the study concludes the condition of people who are living near Pilibhit Tiger Reserve in drastic situations. One of the many reasons is that they are not aware of policies and programs made for them and also they had to leave their homes and properties to live a life free of fear of animal attacks and poverty. Those inhabitants, which stayed near the tiger reserve have constant fear of attacks from the big- cats. Apart from this, now they cannot enter into the forest land, where they used to go to fetch rare

“Katarua”, wood and medicinal herbs. The lives of many people entirely used to depend on these things. So now they are left with no main source of income. Although the government has been trying every possible way to lift the socio-economic conditions of the people living here, but due to lack of awareness, the people are not acquainted with government initiatives. We can help them by informing them about the schemes and programs being run for their well-being.

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